

Corporal Punishment is a Boon or A Bane for School Students - A Comparative Study

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Abstract

The present article explains both the aspects of corporal punishment in school education. It predicts the positive and negative impact over a child. It is a simply comparative study of student's development during the corporal punishments and after banning the corporal punishments. Children are the future generation of India but they should be inculcated in such way to bring overall development in all aspects. The emotional, social, cultural, thinking aspects are essential for making a child into a responsible citizen of India. Discipline is the base of education and education is the base of physical as well as mental development. Without discipline we cannot achieve the goal of education. Punishment and discipline are the two facets of the same coin. Quoting the verdict of Supreme court of India, imposing ban on punishment in schools, Is it possible for the school authority to maintain discipline in the school? How can we bring discipline in schools without punishment?. Children of the schools are well aware of the fact that teachers have no right for cane beating and giving any kind of corporal punishment. So, the children disobey teachers, elders and their parents. Due to imposing ban on punishments, children don't adhere to the rules and regulations of the school and creating indiscipline as much as they can. The whole education system became only for name sake.

Gap between the teacher and student increased

Nowadays, we cannot find any involvement of teacher and students in the teaching-learning process. The role of teachers shrank to minimum extent. Here a question arises, how can you face the challenges of misbehaving children in the school to restore complete discipline in the school. As far as possible, the concerned students are advised but sometimes their deeds go to the level of extreme condition such as physical assault among the children. In such circumstances, the principal or the teacher find no other way except the intrusion of police. There are many incidents of children attacking teachers which is unfortunate for the education. How can you deal with all those situations? So, abide by the Supreme Court order, teachers restrict themselves only to classroom teaching not indulging in other aspects of maintaining discipline or developing other skills. There are many instances where a strong physical assault between two students going on in front of the teacher but what he can do? Other than watching. So, the role of teacher in other areas go to zero levels. Nowadays, one small cane beating dragged the teachers to police station and registered FIR. Such type of immature activities makes education useless and futile.

Corporal Punishment is a Boon for the Students

Even on today, there are million of parents who favour corporal punishment. They can better reason for imposing corporal punishment. How a clay can be moulded into a good statue without touching or beating?. So, without punishment child can't realize the difference between good and bad deeds. Giving over freedom and rights to children will bring a bad impact on the development of children. In the past, a fifth class pass out can read and write a paragraph in English but at present there are many students even at class X who can't read a paragraph in any languages. In majority of cases, the corporal punishment proved and earned a better result. Due to fear of teachers the children kept themselves away from wrong doing. Hence, the corporal punishment helped a lot in improving the discipline in the schools as well as in their career. The children more beaten means more care. In many occasion parents give the whole responsibility of their children to the teachers for making them into a good citizen of India.

Corporal Punishment is a Curse for the Students

There are few groups of people who bat for against the corporal punishment in schools. By analyzing certain aspects, everyone will support for banning of corporal punishment in school. In the modern world, adopting family planning norms, in each family restricts to one or two children. So, the parents love their children and want to give more happiness in their life. Under these circumstances, they cannot tolerate anyone else beating their child irrespective of any reason. Now the parents lost their hope over teacher and they want to nurture their children as they want to be. So, if we go through both the aspects one thing is getting clear here that is time has changed, as a part of it thinking also get changed. There are many incidents which reveals sometimes the teacher has beaten a child severely and lead to coma stage. In one more occasion, a teacher touched a student with red hot iron rod for stealing question papers. Such type of life-threatening punishments moved the supreme court to ban corporal punishment in schools. Nowadays teachers are more oriented to self-centric and thinking of their own but not the betterment of their school children. In many occasion teacher himself not leading a disciplined life then how can they advise their children?

Conclusion

It is a great topic for a good debate. In the past, you can find many dedicated teachers only thinking for the benefit of their children but at present the teachers are more on self-centric. They have no time to think and form some strategy for the improvement of weak students. So, at the past they possessed the right of cane beating approved by their parents. On the contrast, in the present scenario with lot of characterless teachers who are paid for teaching your children. The teacher should be a role model for their children but nowadays you find very few of them. By analyzing the both part of corporal punishment in schools I concluded that corporal punishment is needless but on the other hand it should not be completely wiped off. With the provision in some extreme cases it needs but it can be executed by the Principal or Head of the schools under care and conscious. Above all in my view, it is the responsibility of parents to show the right path for their children. Finally I must say corporal punishment is a curse for the children of India.

Note: This is not to hurt anybody in any way. The term 'Teacher' used here don't indicate all but few. No doubt there are large number of dedicated teachers still existing in the education system. As a research scholar I salute for those responsible teachers who made a remarkable contribution in the upliftment of children.

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